

Why Human Being is a Composite of Plurality of Forms? – John Pecham's Arguments

Keywords: John Pecham, plurality of substantial forms, Thomas Aquinas, unity of substantial form, body of Christ

Abstract

In this paper, I offer a concise study of John Pecham's views on metaphysics and anthropology. While preparing, I relied on four his works: *Quaestiones tractantes de anima*, *Tractatus de anima*, *Quodlibeta quatuor*, and *Summa de esse et essentia*. I discuss questions regarding the conception of the soul, its origin and division. Next, there is a brief analysis of the views of the Archbishop of Canterbury concerning the problems of matter and theory of the embryo rations (*rationes seminales*). The last chapter hence discusses the problem of a status of the body of Christ at the time between His

death and resurrection in the context of a dispute on the unity and plurality of forms. This topic became the major reason for the dispute between John Pecham and Thomas Aquinas in 1270. The main task of this paper is an attempt to grasp the foundation of John Pecham's thesis on the plurality of forms in human being.

John Pecham is considered a representative of Neoplatonism. On the one hand, he eagerly turns to the authority of Augustine (divine illumination, theory of the embryo rations, unity of soul and its faculties). He also draws from

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the “tradition” of the Franciscan masters, Alexander of Hales and Bonaventure. At the same time, he openly admits his inspirations on the views of Aristotle and Avicenna and especially appreciates Stagirite in solving *stricte* philosophical problems. This specific syncretism and eclecticism are especially visible in his theses on philosophical anthropology (psychology). In analysis of body and soul I may indicate at least three entwined components: Augustinian, Platonic and Avicennian.

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Pecham¹ himself claims that he indebted his views in the domain of psychology (especially on activities and cognition of the soul) to philosophers such as: Augustine, Boethius and Aristotle². Similarly, when it comes to the view on the composition of soul from the form and matter, he calls the names of Avicenna and Boethius, and additionally falsely prescribes to the latter one the views of a Neoplatonic Dominic Gundisalvi expressed in *De unitate et uno*.

Pecham's theses (particularly in domain of metaphysics) clearly show a syncretism of influences characteristic of the Franciscan school of the epoch. I need to agree with G. Melani, an editor of *Tractatus de anima* that on the top-

ic of soul, body and forms, in the views of the Archbishop of Canterbury, three elements intervene: firstly, the Platonic one, when he says that soul essentially differs from body, secondly, the Avicennian, when he offers a definition of life, thirdly, there is a visible influence of the views of Augustine³. The aforementioned views on the creation and origin of the soul remain in a strict dependency on their theological connotations to which conservative theologians of the 12th and 13th centuries sought to be faithful. H. Spettmann speaks of Pecham as of a great proponent of the so-called “old Franciscan school” which actually is a “pre-Thomist” Scholastic⁴.

Pecham points out the dignity and superiority of human souls over other creatures and that God creates them out of nothingness by His singular act of creation. It has to be observed how much attention – following the Augustinian line and his other predecessors – the author turns to the conception of the embryo rations (*rationes seminales*) in the context of the creation of man. Moreover, it is worth mentioning that Pecham draws from the views of Aristotle to justify philosophical and theological theses, for the most part, to attack Thomas Aquinas and his conception of the unity of the substantial form.

¹ The following article refers to the conclusions included in the monography of Dawid Lipski, *Jan Peckham i Tomasz z Akwinu. Spór o jedność formy substancjalnej w człowieku*, [in:] *Opera Philosophorum Medii Aevi*, vol. 15, Warszawa 2015.

² Cfr. *Tractatus de anima Ioannis Pecham*, ed. P.G. Melani, Edizioni Studi francescani, Florence 1948, p. I, c. IV, p. 13-15.

³ Cfr. *Ibidem*, p. I, c. I, p. 4; p. III, c. XIV, p. 47.

⁴ Cfr. H. Spettmann, *Die Psychologie des Johannes Pecham*, w: *Beiträge zur Geschichte der Philosophie und Theologie des Mittelalters* 20 (1919), p. 97.

I. Division of soul in the context of a structure of human being

Pecham asks the question of whether the sensual and vegetative life is prior to the infusion of the rational soul. He assumes that it is more proper to speak that in human being there is one fully animating soul consisted of threefold substance and life that is vegetative, sensual, and rational. On the basis of vegetative and sensual substance, the soul was classified to the species with regard to matter (*materialiter*). On the basis of the rational substance, the soul was classified to the genus with regard to form (*formaliter*). The rational soul has its own sensual faculties (*vires sensitivae*), because it is designed exactly as complementary to (*complementum*) sensual soul⁵.

The author observes that form joins matter with no other separated medium (*medio distinguentis*). However, it is not without mediation of something previously prepared (*medio disponentis*). The vegetative and sensual soul is hence such a disposition or preparation for the intellectual life. To support his reasoning, Pecham turns to the commentary of Averroes⁶, who claims that the vegetative life and the sensual life join with the body through the mediation of the union of rational soul and body. Sensual and vegetable life in a human being is, hence, something more material than reason, nevertheless, more immaterial

than body. There is a following implication for Pecham: we may separate the rational soul, its substance and activity from the body. The vegetative or sensual soul is impossible to detach from the body. We may do so in our cognition in approaching them as species⁷.

In arriving (*adveniens*) at an initiated composition of sensual soul and body, the rational soul does not annihilate a current soul, but actually supplements it (*completur*). That is why the intellectual soul and the prior composition do not create two souls but one, such as human being is one substance consisting of a soul and body composition. The arriving rational soul does not possess any contradiction with regard to the sensual soul. The sensual soul is even a necessary disposition (*dispositio*) to its acceptance. The rational soul maintains hence the born sensual soul (*genita*), which creates a material disposition for the intellect. Thus, if “there is intellect” in some substance, the sensual faculties are regarded as lower ones. However, Pecham clearly points out that the view expressed by some scholars claiming that it is some intentional power (*virtus intentionalis*) that is prior to the infusion (*infusio*) of the rational soul is false. According to the author, the objection explicitly derives from the words of Aristotle⁸. The rational soul, created by

⁵ Cfr. *Johannis Pechami Quaestiones Tractantes de Anima*, ed. H. Spettmann, [in:] *Geschichte der Philosophie des Mittelalters*, 19, 5–6 (Münster 1918), q. III resp., p. 37.

⁶ Pecham points out at commentary on the Nicomachean Ethics (Book VI, chapter 2) quotation not found.

⁷ Cfr. *Johannis Pechami Quaestiones Tractantes de Anima*, q. XXV solutio obiectorum, p. 187.

⁸ See: Aristoteles, *De animalium generatione* 736b.

God, includes hence in itself (*includit in se*), as says Pecham, three natures as three potentialities, not as three substances. The rule is that whatever is attainable for a lower faculty, is also possible for the higher one, not otherwise. Hence, just as the vegetativeness of a plant can animate (*vegetare*) the body, sensuality can animate the body and endow it with sensual faculty (*sensificare*). The latter view seems to be more in agreement with the words of scholars and theologians⁹. Nature governs the most noble subject, the organic body (*corpus organicum*), in a way that it is a disposition for rational life (*vitam rationalem*). Nature, thus, does not create a rational life as it itself is not born to be rational¹⁰. The rational soul cannot derive from another human being.

With regard to the question of whether the rational soul is a form of body and is a body itself at the same, Pecham claims that if, in the order of nature and time, the body had been formed prior to its soul, then we assume that body has its form and matter. Corporeal form hence (*forma corporalis*), especially of the human body, has no resemblance (*comparatio*) to the rational soul. That is why some corporeal form remains after receding the

rational soul. Rational soul, hence, leaves corporeality (*corporeitatis*), whose form is not annihilated through arriving or receding soul, as any soul or higher form is not in itself equipped with corporeality. In the human body, hence, all forms of four elements (*quattuor elementorum*) are reduced to one form of mixture (*forma mixta*). Obviously, this mixture cannot be of any character but proper for the human union. As a consequence, in human being there are numerous forms gradually (ordered) directed to the one ultimate perfection, which is why a man formed according to that pattern is a unity.

Archbishop's explanation on the relation of soul and body is rather vague. He claims that each moment of infusing a rational soul (*appropriatio*) into a human body is direct (*simpliciter*). This body is the most noble and the most balanced relation. Therefore, the soul can use it in a substantial way (*substantialiter*) as a substantial form. Assigning a soul to a particular body is substantial as far as a rational soul turns to this body¹¹. Thus, a form of soul (*forma animae*) is attributed to the matter of a body as to its aim but as to a thing that, in a sense, is needed¹².

2. Matter and theory of the embryo ratios

Pecham analyses the problem concerning the potentiality of the first matter.

Potentiality is its own entire passivity (*mere passiva est*). Hence, on the potenti-

⁹ Nevertheless, this statement is in line with that of Thomas Aquinas. Pecham in presenting a historical approach on vegetativeness, sensuality and rationality (whether they compose one or three substances) only summarizes a pending debate.

¹⁰ Cfr. *Johannis Pechami Quaestiones Tractantes de Anima*, q. I, p. 9-11.

¹¹ Cfr. Fr. Ioannis Pecham, OFM, *Quodlibeta Quattuor*, q. IV ad 20, p. 57.

¹² Cfr. *Ibidem*, q. II ad 27 resp., p. 16.

ality of the first matter, we can say nothing else than it is equipped in the ability to accept form. The problem arises in understanding of what actually Pecham had in mind when he says that *informis materia* in the metaphysical approach is a fundament of all creatures, including the spiritual ones. He repeats a stance, already known in the tradition, on common complexity with form and matter (panhylemorphism) and distinguishes between the first matter form and the matter with a concrete form. There are no prior (*praesae*) dimensions within capabilities (*in viribus*) of the first matter unless regarded in potentiality. Only aftersubstantial elements, distinguished by the form of natural things, can indicate and establish new dimensions. In each body, these quantitative dimensions (*partes quantitativae*) are mostly and directly related to creating a being. In simpler elements, there is “more” matter than in more complex elements¹³. Parts of matter at each particular moment of constituting, are equally diverse (*aequaliter diversae*)¹⁴.

On the question of the origin of matter, Pecham shows that God – if he wants – can derive (*producit*) matter from nothingness, regardless of any form. Even form keeps matter in the completed essence (*conservat in esse completo*). God is able to – as says Pecham – cause the existence of matter without

form as the matter is more dependent on the Creator than on the form¹⁵.

To the question of what are the embryo rations – he answers – that they are the power to give birth to unities. The embryo rations are explained with regard to some existence achieved through the activity of nature. Man and donkey are in agreement in the order of nature. However, in man, we do not find the embryo ratio necessary to bring a donkey to existence as in human being, there is his species with regard to a particular kind of existence (*sub quodam esse*), which cannot be rejected by the corporeal nature of man. However, as Augustine says¹⁶, in a human being, there is an efficient cause (*ratio causalis*), which would be able, through the power of God, to create a donkey. God can change every body into each other one, similarly to Adam's rib, which served as the embryo ratio for the creation of the body of Eve. Nevertheless, such dependency does not take place when an angel and a man are considered. From the power of an angel no human being can come to existence, nor otherwise¹⁷.

The embryo rations are, hence, the power responsible for bringing entities into existence. Moreover, this power is not only the power of giving birth but also indicates a sort of ability of matter and a particular mode of existence. For that reason, something remains an in-

¹³ Pecham follows Aristotle and shows the example comparing water and air (Aristoteles, *De generatione et corruptione*, 333a 22).

¹⁴ Cfr. *Summa de esse et essentia*, ed. F. Delorme, [in:] *Studi franciscani* (25) 1928, p. 64.

¹⁵ Cfr. *Quodlibet Quatuor*, q. 1, p. 175; See also: D. Sharp, *Franciscan philosophy at Oxford in the thirteenth century*, Oxford University Press 1930, p. 180-1.

¹⁶ Following the editor: *Super Genesis ad litteram*, lib. VI, c. 5-14; VII, c. 22, 28; IX, c. 17 et 18.

¹⁷ Cfr. *Summa de esse et essentia*, p. 66.

dividuality of a given genus, and even it differs from the others with regard to species. Thus, when a man dies and his body gets decomposed, an individuum of species turns into ashes, whereas it remains as an individuum of the genus. Should it happen – says Pecham – that ashes turned to wind or to the body of any animal, it would always remain true that matter and substance were previously in the body of some human being. Thus, it is possible that from an individuality of one species would come into existence another individuality (entity) of a given genus. However, there is no such possibility in the order of nature (*secundum naturam*)¹⁸, that from an entity of one genus would come into existence another entity of another genus.

In analysing questions about whether the embryo rations are included in feed or substance giving birth¹⁹, Pecham says that, from the perspective of causes,

they are in the generating substance (*in substantia generantis*), formally hence, in semen as the result of the abundance of nourishment (*de superfluo nutrimenti*)²⁰. Moreover, all the embryo rations carry some resemblance to the Sun. Trees and herbs differ in their transformation under the influence of the Sun but adequately to the intention (*secundum rationem intentionalem*), all are perfected by the sunlight²¹. It seems that the above suggests a similarity to the famous saying of Aristotle – confirmed by Thomas Aquinas – that man is born by man and the Sun²².

The above study allows Pecham to accept the view that the soul is a composition of matter and form, in accordance with the stance of panhylemorphism he expresses. Also, this view, close to the views of Bonaventure and Alexander of Hales, finds its justification in the arguments of their devoted pupil.

3. Ontic status of the body of Christ between death and resurrection

The question regarding the identity of the body of Christ, alive and dead, became the major reason for disagreement between John Pecham and Thomas Aquinas. It concerns not only metaphysical issues but also a domain of theological ones. Pecham speaks of the

views of Thomas and shows its flaws. Thus, he points out the meaning of form *corporeitatis* with regard to the question of the identity of the body of Christ between His death and resurrection.

In analysing the question of unequivocality and ambiguity in explaining the

¹⁸ Cfr. *Ibidem*, p. 67.

¹⁹ *Utrum ratio seminalis hominis sit in alimentis an in substantia generantis*.

²⁰ Cfr. *Quodlibet Quatuor*, q. 12 p. 158.

²¹ Cfr. *Quodlibet Quatuor*, q. 10, p. 30.

²² Cfr. Aristoteles, *Physica* 194b 14. Thomas refers to these words amongst other [in:] *Sententia Metaphysicae*, lib. 7, l.6 n. 21; *De potentia*, q. 3 a. 7 s.c. 3; *De substantiis separatis*, cap. 10 co.; *Summa contra Gentiles*, lib. 3 cap. 69 n. 24; *Summa Theologiae* I, q. 115 a.3 ad 2, and q. 118 a. 1 ad 3.

body of Christ²³ Pecham starts with a thesis that the union of two principles, form and matter, creates the existence (*dat esse*). From the first composition of the first substantial form (*forma prima substantialis*) with the first matter follows unity (at the same time, there is substance and that what is substance). Hence, we may say that a change of forms of natural bodies does not take place with regard to the numerical identity of substance as the state of the body, whether it is “alive” or “dead”, does not concern the essence of corporeality. With regard to a change, at the same time, there remain matter, potentiality and substantial form, as matter alone is not able to be a subject of a change.

On the question of the ontic status of the body of Christ between His death and resurrection, it is certain, according to the author, that Christ truly adopted human nature. After death, hence, He was deprived of human nature, as He was not a man, according to a common opinion of scholars. He also was not a living being during these three days (*in triduo*), nor did he have an animated body (*corpus animatum*). Neither had he any body as he did not belong to the genus of living beings. Thus – as Pecham summarizes – during the three days between His death and the resurrection, Christ was neither a human being nor

a living being nor an animated body as far as we use this term equivocally. Additionally, ambiguity allows to denote it as the body of a living being. Moreover – as Pecham says – it is commonly known that when dead bodies are concerned, we speak of twofold decomposition. Firstly, within the frame of human nature when soul and body are separated, and secondly, regarding the decomposition of a decaying body and its elements (*elementa*). Former separation would regard Christ, the latter one not, because His body was protected by the Divine nature from further decomposition. Thus, the scope of changes in the body of Christ as a result of His death was lesser than in any other human body concerned. This analysis led Pecham to the conclusion that the eye of Christ, alive and dead, can be denoted with the common name only equivocally as in both of these “states”, not only was it not the same eye, but also it was not an eye in a strict sense. However, the aforementioned eye, in both cases, was the same part of the human body. That is why each human body, as far as it is a body, numerically is considered to be the same body, both alive and dead²⁴.

It seems that the essence of this problem, according to Pecham, is that Thomas Aquinas did not take into consideration a view on the hierarchy of

²³ Essentially we focus here on a *responsio* of a question: *Utrum oculus dicatur de oculo Christi vivo et mortuo univoce vel aequivoco* (*Quodlibet Quatuor*, q. 11, p. 196-202). As points out Gordon Wilson *Quodlibet IV (Romanum)* is a direct answer and a criticism outspoken by Pechama with regard to the words of Thomas in a dispute on the unity of forms included in the III part *Summa teologiae* (Cfr. G. Wilson, *The Critique of Thomas Aquinas's Unicity Theory of Forms in John Pecham's Quodlibet IV (Romanum)*, [in:] *Franciscan Studies* 56 (1998), p. 423-431).

²⁴ Cfr. *Utrum oculus dicatur de oculo Christi vivo et mortuo univoce vel aequivoco* (*Quodlibet Quatuor*, q. 11, p. 196-202).

forms, and as a consequence, rejection of the form *corporeitatis* in the structure of man and Christ Himself. The absence of the form, would allow to maintain a numerical identity of the alive and dead

body and leads, according to Pecham, to numerous difficulties, including the possibility of undermining the reasonability of the cult of relics.

4. Conclusions

Pecham accepts the plurality of forms organised hierarchically in human being because each of them determines matter proper to itself (potentiality). Each further form is an act with regard to lower forms, and also a potentiality for further perfection. Thus, in the moment of joining the corporeality the rational soul, does not annihilate its form but maintains it in its existence. Corporeality is determined by the form of corporeality, not by the higher form, which does not have corporeality in itself. The very corporeality is, according to the author, “anticipated” in the very definition of soul expressed by Aristotle in *De anima*. Similar forms of elements remain in the form of mixture (*mixta*). Pecham excludes from one being only these forms which are contrary to each other, for example, “animateness” and “inanimateness”. Hence, the general assumption follows that in human being, there are numerous forms gradually subordinated (*ordinatae*) to one ultimate perfection. Starting from the form of elements and the mixture ordering its forms (*forma mixta*), through the form of corporeality, the form of vegetativeness, the form of sensuality, and then the rational form as the perfection of finality.

Pecham points out that the body is formed prior to the soul and remains even after the soul recedes. Secondly, the matter has some entitative existence. It, however, in itself essentially (*essentialiter*) distinguishes from the form.

According to Pecham, *rationes seminales* are a power which indicates some ability of matter and a particular mode of existence. As a consequence, even after the moment of decomposition, human body remains an individuum of the genus but of different species. On the one hand, Pecham stresses that we cannot speak of the body, that is deprived of soul and that both of these natures are mutually defined, and their relation is direct. What is more, he claims that when we define a body without its soul, it leads to ambiguity. On the other hand, he points out that the body is the most noble and the most balanced union. That is why a soul is able to use, or as Augustine prefers to say – govern a body in a substantial way (*substantialiter*) as a substantial form.

With regard to the ontic status of Christ between His dead and resurrection Pecham shows that Christ lost His human nature and his body did not belong to living entities. It does not belong to the genus of human bodies and

cannot be denoted a body unequivocally but only ambiguously. However, each alive and dead body, as far as it remains a body and does not undergo further decomposition, numerically remains the same substance. It happens through a form *corporeitatis*, which maintains the material identity of subjects in both aforementioned cases. Moreover, the body of Christ, contrary to other dead bodies, was protected from further changes thanks to its divine nature.

Pecham assumes that after the moment of “infusion,” the rational soul remains the form of *corporeitatis*. Nature

demands the continuation of its existence if the body is to be considered one of the components of a human being. Otherwise, we will face contradiction with numerous theological theses, such as the resurrection of Christ or the resurrection of the dead²⁵. Thus, I need to agree with D. Douie who says that on the question of the relation of the soul to its powers, Pecham is essentially Augustinian. Nevertheless, on the question of the relation of soul and body, in attempting to reconcile Platonism with Aristotelianism, his stance seems to be rather vague²⁶.

²⁵ Cfr. D. Sharp, *ibidem*, p. 187.

²⁶ Cfr. D. Douie, *Archbishop Pecham*, Oxford 1952, p. 19.

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